

Preliminary research on the use of portable vector network analyzers working with two measurement coils to determine the impedance of networks that are difficult to access

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Abstract — Accurate grid impedance measurement is essential for managing modern electrical grids, especially regarding compliance with CISPR standards for EMC emissions. This article presents a network impedance measurement method using a vector network analyzer (VNA) cooperating with two coil probes placed on a section of the tested grid. The method has potential applications for real-time network monitoring and EMC compliance; hence it can be used to detect faults in real grids. A minimally sized artificial network is proposed to test the correctness of this method. This artificial network can also be used to optimise the measurement system, including selecting coils for operation in a given frequency range.

Keywords — wideband impedance measurement, VNA applications, current injection probes, EMC standards

I. INTRODUCTION

In industrial and power environments, particularly those involving large-scale and high-power equipment, accurately assessing electromagnetic emissions is critical for maintaining safe and compliant operations. Such environments, defined by high short-circuit power levels and frequent transient disturbances—often due to renewable energy sources and power converters—are classified as harsh due to their significant challenges for emission intensity and measurement. Traditional testing methods may fall short in these contexts, prompting the need for specialized, in situ methodologies.

This work focuses on the development of traceable electromagnetic emission measurement techniques adapted to harsh environments, specifically targeting frequencies from 10 kHz to 30 MHz with a target maximum uncertainty level of 6 dB. Primary objectives include methods for measuring impedance in situ, establishing correlations between laboratory and field studies, and understanding the effects of interference variables and background noise. To achieve these goals, the task structure includes on-site impedance measurements, conducted and radiated emission methods, and validation techniques based on CISPR 16 standards [1,2].

The goal of these methods is to create reliable and standardized test procedures that can cope with the complexity of real-world high-power installations. Ultimately, this research will contribute to the development of the CISPR 37 standard, supporting greater compliance and operational integrity in demanding industrial environments.

Several works talk about the use of a vector network analyzer (VNA) with a pair of coils to measure impedance and interference in networks [3,4]. This work complements basic research and goes towards the development of conducted emission research methods in the common current flow model (CM) [1].

II. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

A. General Scheme

The research within the described method is aimed at measuring impedance in difficult industrial conditions and with difficult access to the section of the tested network, hence the parallel variant of electrical coil probes arrangement [5,6,7] was adopted, as shown on the left in Fig. 1 [3]. They are placed perpendicularly in laboratory conditions to minimize their mutual induction [4]. The detailed measurement diagram shown on the right side of Fig. 1 takes into account the influence of the mutual impedance of the coils.

Fig. 1. A general schematic diagram on the left and a detailed diagram on the right of network impedance measurement using two electrical coil probes and a vector network analyzer.

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Fig. 2. The method of calculating the scattering parameters of the network by the VNA and the formula for the impedance of the unknown network Z_x when measuring S-parameters with an analyzer with a pair of coils.

B. Maintaining the Integrity of the Specifications

The impedance of the unknown network Z_x is calculated from the scattering parameters S_{ij} measured by the VNA. Fig. 2. shows the measurement scheme and formulas for calculating S parameters performed by the VNA. Formula (1) is used to calculate the impedance of the unknown network Z_x using the VNA and two coils attached to the two ports of the analyzer [3,4].

$$Z_x = K \left(\frac{S_{11}+1}{S_{21}} \right) - Z_{setup} \quad (1)$$

When one of the coils injects a signal from the VNA generator into the network circuit, the other receives a signal from the network and passes it to the VNA measurement circuits. Based on these signals, the analyzer calculates S parameters, which are substituted into the formula (1), where Z_x is the impedance of the measured network, Z_{setup} is the impedance inserted into the system by the introduction of the measuring circuit, K is the processing coefficient of the function of the measured parameters S. By creating a network with a known impedance value, for example, by simulating a short circuit ($Z_x=0$) and then connecting an element with a known impedance value over the entire operating frequency range, for example, 50Ω , two equations can be created, the solution of which will be the values of K and Z_{setup} [3,4].

III. DESCRIPTION OF THE EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS OF MEASUREMENTS

In the experiment described below, an approach was taken to any arbitrarily selected electrically conductive network. In the first approach, one cable was selected, in the target measurement with heavy industrial conditions, often with difficult access to it. On a straight section of this cable, two electrical coils will be installed as far apart as possible (a repetitive distance of 25 cm between their axes of symmetry was assumed). A portable VNA will be connected to the coils, which will measure the scattering parameters of the S_{11} and S_{21} networks, and these will allow estimating the impedance of this network.

A. Artificial Network Proposal

Since we are to deal with arbitrary electrical networks, the smallest artificial network allowing setup elements was proposed, made of a conductive rod in the form of a 50x25 cm rectangular loop. A photo of the network and the result of its measurement made with a VNA type ENA E5080A in the frequency range from 10 kHz to 30 MHz in the form of a Smith chart is shown in Fig. 3. The artificial network made in this way is inductive in nature with an inductance of about 19 μ H. For low frequencies (10 kHz and below) it behaves as a short circuit, and at 30 MHz its impedance is about 2 k Ω .

Fig. 3. The 50x25 cm artificial network and measurement of its parameters with the VNA.

B. Constituent Setup Elements for Conducting Basic Research

Since the experiment assumed the use of the setup described below for impedance measurements in any electrical network, an artificial network with the smallest dimensions suitable for carrying out this experiment was proposed.

The setup shown in Fig. 4. for conducting basic research under laboratory conditions includes:

- ENA E5080A type VNA with a possible operating frequency range from 9 kHz to 4.5 GHz.
- A pair of electric coils, input type CIP 9136 with a possible frequency range of 10 kHz to 400 MHz [8] and output type CSP 9160 with a possible frequency range of 10 kHz to 100 MHz [9].
- Artificial network 50 x 25 cm.

Before starting the method correctness tests, the coil parameters were measured: insertion loss (IL) of the current injection coil (upper graph in Fig. 4) and transfer impedance (TI) of the receiving coil (lower graph). Both quantities show changes in the range of test frequencies. Hence, even for a completely resistive network, where the impedance is independent of frequency, the K and Z_{setup} parameters will change with the change of frequency, because S_{11} and S_{21} will not be constant in this frequency range (they also depend on IL and TI).

C. Measurements Using the Artificial Network

First, the artificial network was measured using the VNA with two coils under short-circuit and open-circuit conditions and compared with the result of direct measurement of the network by the VNA. The comparison result is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4. The components of the setup and the frequency characteristics of the coils used [8,9].

Fig. 5. Comparison of the measurement results of the artificial network (on the left) directly by the VNA and (on the right) through two coils, one injecting the signal from the analyzer and the other receiving it for two variants of operation of the short-circuited and open-circuited network.

Then, the measurement was performed using all the elements of the setup, including two resistances of zero ohms by shorting the network and 50 Ω. The setups with these resistance connection variants and the measurement result are presented in Fig. 6. The presented frequency characteristic clearly shows the impact on its change when the resistance is changed, in other words, the change in the resistance connected to the network is observable in the S parameters measured by the VNA.

Fig. 6. Short circuit of the network (red) and connecting a standard resistance of 50 Ω to it (yellow) and the result of their measurement by the VNA with two measurement coils.

Fig. 7. Measurements with various impedance elements. VNA: ENA E5080, measurement range from 10 kHz to 30 MHz, with two passive electric coils: CIP 9136 input, CSP 9160 output and artificial network 50 x 25 cm. Abscissa - frequency - linear.

In this way, the study of the impact of various RLC elements on network behaviour and the differentiation of changes in these elements by the VNA in the proposed setup began. In Fig. 7. three frequency characteristics of the network scattering parameter S_{21} obtained by measurement with the VNA with the measuring coils for a capacitor connected to the network with a capacity of 12 pF and an inductance of 0.5 μH are presented. The first graph compares the open loop measurement of the network with the case of connecting a capacitor as a short of the loop. The second graph compares switching on the same capacitor with its short circuit. The third graph compares the inductance with its short circuit in the artificial network loop.

Fig. 8 and 9 show the results of measuring the scattering parameters of S_{11} and S_{21} in the form of their moduli as a function of frequency, in a system as previously described with the difference that a portable miniature VNA of the DeepVNA 101 V.3.2 type was used, and the resistance was

Fig. 8. Graph comparing the frequency response of the S_{11} scattering parameter module (reflection coefficient, input impedance) of a two-port DUT device consisting of two coils and an artificial network with connected various resistances.

changed from zero to infinity in the artificial network. Based on these results, it was decided to check the correctness of the calculation of formula (1). The results of the parameters S_{11} and S_{21} at a frequency of about 310 kHz for a resistance of 50 Ω were $-0.5536 + i0.3065$ and $-0.0043 - i0.0084$, respectively, and for a resistance of 150 Ω $-0.5145 + i0.4161$ and $-0.0012 - i0.0034$. Based on these results, the module of the constants $|K| = 0.3536$ Ω and $|Z_{\text{setup}}| = 11.46$ Ω were determined from formula (1). The S-parameters for the 100 Ω resistor were measured: $S_{11} = -0.5222 + i0.3844$ and $S_{21} = -0.0019 - i0.0049$. After putting the above data into formula (1), the deviation of the calculated value from the 100 Ω value was 0.42%. With frequency, the deviation increased. For a frequency of ten times, about 3 MHz, the deviation was about 2%, and at the end of the range at about 30 MHz it was even higher. However, the greatest measurement uncertainty according to this method occurs at low frequencies, well below 100 kHz.

The final uncertainty of the above measurements consists of a standard uncertainty derived from S-parameter measurements and the repeatability of the given measurement setup. In our case, the measurements were done in a laboratory setting with a fixed setup, so the repeatability contribution was negligible. The biggest contributors to the final uncertainty are the uncertainties of measured S_{11} at low frequencies and S_{21} at higher frequencies. This is due to a high reflection coefficient (higher than 0.5 in linear terms) of the current injecting probe at low frequencies and a high attenuation measured through the receiving probe.

Fig. 9. Graph comparing the frequency response of the S_{21} dissipation parameter module (forward voltage gain, attenuation) of a two-port DUT device consisting of two coils and an artificial network with connected various resistances.

IV. CONCLUSION

Using the VNA with two measuring coils attached, one of which injects a signal from the internal generator of the VNA, and the other one receives the signal and provides it to the VNA, to measure the impedance of an unknown electrical network is a promising approach. The test results show that the impedance of an unknown network is recognizable. However, for more accurate measurements, it is necessary to monitor the quality of the S parameters as a function of frequency due to the occurrence of resonances and the loss of stable measurements in the area of higher loss of the coils used, where a higher noise-to-signal ratio appears. This is especially important when using portable VNA, where some specification parameters can be worse compared to laboratory VNA. The advantage of this method is the ability to work on an insulated wire of any live network without major interference with the network.

It is therefore acknowledged that this method (as any other VNA two-probe method) suffers from limited performance of the instrumentation. Deterioration of the signal-to-noise ratio causes worsening of results obtained by the VNA through mathematical manipulation of raw quantities, quite sensitive to outliers and weird data behaviour. In this specific example of the setup, there is a problem with the correct reading of network parameters below the frequency of 100 kHz, caused by too high insertion losses of the measurement coils reducing the overall sensitivity as they combine with the worse VNA performance as well.

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